

Attitude of Students towards E-learning and its Impact on their Study Habits: A Meta-Analysis

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ABSTRACT: Students' attitude regarding e-learning and its impact on their study habits have undergone a lot of changes because of the rapid introduction of e-learning into educational systems. In order to examine the relationship between students' perception of e-learning and their study habits, this meta-analysis collects and reviews data from empirical studies published between 2010 and 2025. Qualitative case studies, cross-sectional surveys, quasi-experimental designs, correlational research, and mixed-methods investigations are some of the methodological approaches employed in the reviewed studies. The studies additionally employ research instruments like validated attitude scales, semi-structured interviews, and structured questionnaires. The overall findings reveal generally good attitude of students towards e-learning, with many studies demonstrating notable improvements in study habits and academic engagement because of e-learning integration. These improvements include improved motivation, efficient time management, and adaptive learning techniques made possible by AI and digital tools. However, some studies demonstrate the intricate effects of e-learning environments by addressing issues with technology restraints and various degrees of student preparedness. The results highlight the need for educational interventions that promote positive attitudes toward e-learning and support effective study methods for greater academic success in digital learning environments.

KEY WORDS: Digital education, E-learning, Online learning, Student attitudes, Study habits.

INTRODUCTION

The rapid development of information and communication technology in the twenty-first century has led to a rise in the daily usage of digital devices for a variety of purposes in both formal and informal education as well as the workplaces. Since the advent of information and communication technology (ICT), students studying in colleges and universities around the world have witnessed significant changes (Bassey et al., 2007). Students are now able to attend lectures without physically seeing the teacher in their homes or classrooms. E-learning as an element of ICT has transformed the way of students' study. (Bassey & colleagues, 2007). Any learning that is made accessible by technology can be described as e-learning in its broadest description. E-learning encompasses a wide variety of instructional tools and methods that are continually evolving to meet the demands of teachers and students. It covers three main areas: broadening training and knowledge prospects; improving educational quality; and the need for TEIs to gain and keep an edge in a cut-throat market in order to bring in more students (Newton, 2003). This approach provides students a greater control over their education by allowing them to get involved with various courses wherever and whenever they choose. They can also compile all the material they need for their studies whenever they are free (Liu & Wang, 2009).

Study habits are the practices or approaches one uses while studying; these are the habits that have been developed throughout one's time in school. Study habits can be of two types good and bad study habits. Good study habits include taking notes thoroughly each day, reading textbooks, paying careful attention in class, and keeping record of everything. Skipping class, ignoring assignments, watching TV, or playing video games in place of studying are instances of poor study habits. Study habits and students' attitudes towards e-learning are closely related. Proactive learning habits, such as persistent involvement in online forums and effective time management, are linked with positive attitudes. Negative attitudes, on the other hand, can lead to boredom, procrastination, and a reliance on less effective study techniques. In order to enhance academic performance, Gogus & Gunes (2011) highlighted the importance of aligning online teaching methods with students' study habits and learning styles. Students who opt e-learning had better study habits and achievement in school, Kumari (2022). Kumar & Pandey (2024) conducted a study and the findings revealed that most of the university students exhibited a positive attitude towards e-learning with almost 60 percent of respondents responding positively.

A meta-analysis comparing traditional and blended learning was conducted by Z. Yu et al., (2022). They found that students' attitudes of online learning approaches were mostly favourable. These attitudes were major signs of students' readiness to participate and gain from online learning, which boosted the learning outcomes and improved study habits. Akinlabi, O., and Adedoyin, O. B. (2025) performed a systematic meta-analysis on study habits. The results showed positive correlation between academic success in e-learning environments and effective study habits. Students spent minimal time learning on their own despite having access to technology, and access to technology did not significantly improve study habits across all groups, showing a limited impact of e-learning on study behavior Amin et al. (2021). On the other hand, developing effective study habits can lead to a more positive attitude towards e-learning. Students having good study habits are more likely to have a positive attitude towards e-learning settings, Arulkadacham (2024). Ward et al. (2025) found that 83 percent of students who used AI tools in their study routines improved their study habits and academic performance. Given the varied results found in existing research, there is a clear need to synthesize these findings through a comprehensive review.

Several studies (e.g., Dhiman Kar & Birbal Saha 2014; Srivara Buddhi & A. Dharanipriya 2020; Ding Aixia & Dan Wang 2011) exhibit a strong positive attitude towards e-learning, others (e.g. Eraslan & Topkaya 2017; Behera et., 2016; Gullu et al., 2022) exhibit unfavourable attitude of students towards e-learning. (Kaur 2024; Kumari 2022; Ifeoma et al., 2018) showed positive impact of e-learning on study habits of students.

In the light of these divergent perspectives, this meta-analysis seeks to systematically examine the attitude of students towards e-learning and its impact on their study habits. It draws on findings from 16 empirical studies that were selected for their methodological clarity and relevance in various academic, cultural, and educational contexts. Both qualitative and quantitative studies involving secondary and post-secondary and higher education students are represented in the reviewed literature.

The main objective of this meta-analysis is to find common trends, identify significant factors, and examine the conditions in which e-learning impacts study habits. The insights gathered are meant to help educators, academic advisers, and policy makers in improving e-learning strategies for improved learning results and student engagement.

METHODOLOGY

A systematic, evidence-based approach was employed in this meta-analysis to uncover, examine, and summarize empirical data about the connection between students' attitude towards e-learning and its influence on their study habits. Using university library repositories and online scholarly databases including Google Scholar, ResearchGate, and JSTOR, an extensive literature review was carried out. To maximize coverage, the search included Boolean operators (e.g., AND, OR) with important key terms such as Study habits, E-learning, Student attitudes, Online learning and Digital education.

Initially, the titles, abstracts, and keywords of more than forty articles published between 2010 and 2025 were screened. After assessing the content relevance, sixteen studies were picked for inclusion after removing the duplicates. The inclusion criteria were as follows:

- The selected studies specifically addressed the research issues with an emphasis student's attitude towards e-learning and how it influenced their study habits or learning behaviors.
- The studies included empirical data (quantitative, qualitative, or mixed methods).
- There was satisfactory methodological transparency (e.g., sample size, tools, analysis techniques).

The included studies represented an array of research approaches and spanned a number of countries and academic levels, from secondary education to higher education. A uniform procedure was used to extract the data, which included information about the author or authors, the year, the research design, the characteristics of the sample, the instruments used, and the main findings.

A qualitative synthesis approach was adopted due to the heterogeneity of study designs and measures used in various studies. The current study thematically analyzed and contrasted findings across contexts instead of performing statistical meta-analysis (e.g., effect size pooling). Consistency patterns, contradictions, and contextual factors (such as cultural, technical, or motivating elements) were identified in order to make significant conclusions.

This integrative approach addressed the complexity and diversity of educational environments while providing a deep understanding of student's attitude towards e-learning and its impact on study habits. Cross-study analysis was made possible by the structured comparative matrix, which additionally made it possible to interpret the results in relation with the vast educational literature.

Meta-Analysis

S. No	Name of the Articles	Nature of the Study	Authors & Year	Sample and Instruments	Findings
1.	Assessing attitudes, readiness and motivation of students towards E-learning: A qualitative case study in Uttar Pradesh, India.	Qualitative case study	Kumar & Pandey 2024	45 postgraduate students from a number of professions went through semi-structured interviews as part of a qualitative case study technique. Instrument: Semi structured interviews.	60% of respondents responded positively. However, only a small percentage of students had a neutral or negative attitude for reasons primarily related to technical limitations.
2.	Attitude of University Students towards E-learning in West Bengal.	Survey	Dhiman Kar & Birbal Saha 2014	308 University level students from four Universities namely Sidho-Kanho-Birsha University, Jadavpur University, Visva-Bharati and Gourbanga University were participants of the study. Instrument: Researcher developed questionnaire.	The result revealed that students' have high attitude towards e learning and their attitude scores did not differ significantly with their personal variables such as, gender, stream of study and residence.
3.	Attitude of UG Students Towards E-learning	Quasi-experimental	S. Srivara Buddhi Bhuvaneswari & A. Dharanipriya. 2020	60 first-year undergraduate students of Agriculture College & Research Institute, Coimbatore were selected for the study. Instrument: Self developed attitude scale.	The study inferred that majority of the students were found to have moderate to highly favourable attitude towards e-Learning.
4.	Factors Influencing Learner Attitudes Toward E-learning and Development of E-learning Environment Based on the Integrated E-learning Platform	Quantitative	Ding Aixia & Dan Wang. 2011	128 college students from various majors of Ningbo University ,79 of whom were female and 49 of whom were male with ages ranging between 19 to 22 were asked to complete surveys. Instrument: Structured questionnaire.	Findings demonstrated highly positive attitude about using an online learning environment. The assertion that e-learning has boosted student interest and learning effectiveness was one that many students concurred with. However, a larger percentage (27.4%) of comments demonstrated the adverse impact of e-learning on user learning.

5.	EFL Students' Attitudes towards e-Learning and Effect of an Online Course on Students' Success in English.	Quantitative	Eraslan & Topkaya. 2017	The sample for the present study consisted of 47 state university students. Instrument: Comparative Learning Environment Questionnaire (CLEQ).	The results revealed that though students' attitudes regarding online courses are slightly good, but they don't enhance their overall performance in preparatory classes.
6.	Attitude of B.Ed. Student-Teachers towards E-Learning.	Quantitative	Behera et al., 2016	230 B.Ed. student-teachers from colleges (both urban and rural) affiliated with Sidho-Kanho-Birsha University in the Purulia District of West Bengal were taken as sample. Instrument: Self-developed attitude scale	The results revealed that B.Ed. student teachers in West Bengal's Purulia District possess an attitude towards e-learning that is neither more favourable nor less favourable. The study also found no significant differences in the attitudes of Arts and Science B.Ed. student-teachers toward e-learning.
7.	Determining attitudes toward e-learning: what are the attitudes of health professional students?	Cross-sectional	Gullu et al., 2022	320 undergraduate students from a state university's Faculty of Health Sciences, Nursing Department, formed the studies sample. Instrument: Standardized attitude questionnaire called ASEL (Attitude Scale for E-Learning) developed by Haznedar and Baran (2012).	The findings revealed that 55.3% of students (177) possessed an unfavourable attitude towards online education. Students between the age group of 25 and 29 had significantly greater attitude scores than those between the age groups of 17 and 20 and 21 and 24 (p = 0.002). Students who used computers had considerably higher attitude scores than those without computers (p= 0.001).
8.	Exploring the Efficacy, Attitude, and Challenges of Experiencing the Current EdTech Trends in English Language Learning.	Mixed-methods	Yadav & Albatti 2025	Seven students took part in a semi-structured interview and 75 students from a range of academic fields completed the questionnaires. Instruments: Structured questionnaire/ Semi-structured interviews.	The findings revealed that students frequently utilized EdTech tools, according to descriptive statistics. For instance, 96.1% of students stated that they used digital resources to enhance their speaking, listening, writing, and reading language.
9.	Attitude Towards E-Learning in Relation to Study Habits Among College Students.	Correlational	Kaur 2024	The 292 college students from 11 Punjabi colleges were selected as sample for the study. Instrument: Questionnaire.	The findings demonstrated that attitudes with regard to e-learning differed significantly depending on whether one had better, good, or worse study habits. Furthermore, it was found that college students who have better study habits have a higher attitude toward e-learning.

10.	“Impact of E-learning on study habit and academic achievement of adolescent students	Experimental	Kumari 2022	800 Patna district students were chosen at random as a sample. Instruments: An academic achievement form, a humanized habit list, and a self-made e-learning questionnaire.	The results revealed that although the study habits of adolescents appeared to be appropriate, the impact of e-learning on them was found to be significantly high.
11.	Impact of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) on the Study Habits of Students of Iganmode Grammar School, Ota, Ogun State of Nigeria.	Descriptive	Ilo et al., 2018	Twenty-five percent (25%) of the total population was selected for the study, and 300 copies of the questionnaire were given to SS1 students and 250 copies were given to SS2 students. Instrument: Structured questionnaire.	The study found a strong positive correlation between students' better study habits and their utilization of ICT. Fifty-two (31.9%) of the respondents used ICT to compare notes from lectures, while 156 (32.7%) use it to read various materials online. Others use it for chat, email, and various other tasks.
12.	Analyzing the Impact of AI Tools on Student Study Habits and Academic Performance.	Mixed-methods	Ward et al., 2025	71 university students from various demographics were selected for sample of the study. Instruments: A Likert scale survey and Follow-up interviews.	The findings revealed that 83% of students who used AI tools in their study routines improved their academic performance. 35% showed a modest improvement and 48% reported a significant improvement. Only seventeen percent of respondents said their academic performance was unchanged.
13.	Social Media and Students' Study Habits in Secondary Schools in Bukwo District, Uganda.	Correlational	Kursoro 2019	375 students in Bukwo District, Uganda, formed the sample size. Instruments: Interview guide and self-administered questionnaire.	The results of the study demonstrated that social media was frequently used for a variety of purposes. Students have good study habits (mean of 3.18). $R= 0.985$ and the R^2 value of 0.985 at the significance level of 0.000 supported the correlation results, which reveals a substantial association between social media and students' study habits.

14.	The impact of ICT on students' study habits. Case study: University of Buea, Cameroon.	Survey	Mbah 2010	Out of the 186 students enrolled in the CST/Biology department, 100 students were selected as the sample size. Instrument: Structured questionnaire.	The results showed that students generally have a positive outlook towards ICT and use them to improve learning. As a result, based on the kind of ICT they use to aid in their studies, students frequently change their study habits.
15.	Integration of e-learning system and its effect to the study habits and participation of junior high school students.	Descriptive-correlational	Hero et al., 2021	One hundred and twelve (112) junior high school students from one private school in the Obando, Bulacan, Philippines district made up the study's sample. Instrument: Survey questionnaire.	The findings of the research revealed that e-learning system is effective, reliable, useable, and functional. High school students have good study habits and they frequently engage in class debates. Furthermore, a high or significant correlation was found between students' study habits and the integration of the e-learning system.
16.	Dental Students' Study Habits in Flipped/ Blended Classrooms and Their Association with Active Learning Practices.	Correlational	Amyot et al., 2017	Two classes of second year dental students (SP14, n=106) and (SP15, n=106) were chosen as a convenience sample for the study. Instrument: Questionnaire.	In comparison to 62% of the SP14 class, 72% of the SP15 class reported watching all or more than half of the scheduled lectures, with the majority watching multiple lectures every week. Students in SP14 and SP15 responded that they were unlikely to read the assigned readings prior to the class.

COMPARISON OF THE ARTICLES

This meta-analysis synthesizes findings from sixteen (n=16) empirical studies conducted across varied educational levels and cultural contexts to examine the relationship between e-learning and study habits. The reviewed studies range from correlational to experimental designs and mixed-methods investigations. The comparison highlights common trends, methodological variations, and contextual influences shaping the relationship between student's attitudes towards e-learning and study habits.

Most of the studies exhibited a positive attitude of students towards e-learning and positive impact of e-learning on study habits. For example, Kumar & Pandey (2024), in a qualitative case study involving forty-five (n=45) postgraduate students in Uttar Pradesh from a number of professions, found 60% positive responses with regard to attitude of students towards e-learning and only a small percentage of students had a neutral or negative attitude for reasons primarily related to technical limitations. Similarly, Kar & Saha (2014), conducted a survey study among three hundred eight (n=308) University level students from four Universities namely Sidho-Kanho-Birsha University, Jadavpur University, Visva-Bharati and Gourbanga University found high attitude of students towards e learning and their attitude scores did not differ significantly with their personal variables such as, gender, stream of study and residence.

Bhuaneswari & Dharanipriya (2020), conducted quasi-experimental research among sixty (n=60) first-year undergraduate students of Agriculture College & Research Institute, Coimbatore. The findings revealed that majority of the students were found to have moderate to highly favourable attitude towards e-Learning.

Aixia & Wang (2011), in their quantitative study among one hundred twenty-eight (n=128) college students from various disciplines of Ningbo University found highly positive attitude about using an online learning environment. However, a larger percentage (27.4%) of comments demonstrated an adverse impact of e-learning on user learning.

Despite the general trend of positive associations, some studies reported contrasting results. Eraslan & Topkaya (2017), conducted a quantitative study with sample of forty-seven (n=47) state university students found that though students' attitudes regarding online courses were slightly good, but they did not enhance their overall performance in preparatory classes.

Behera et al. (2016), in their quantitative study including a sample of two hundred thirty (n=230) B.Ed. student-teachers from colleges (both urban and rural) affiliated with Sidho-Kanho-Birsha University in the Purulia District of West Bengal found the attitude towards e-learning neither more favourable nor less favourable. The study also found no significant differences in the attitudes of Arts and Science B.Ed. student-teachers toward e-learning.

On a broader scale, Gullu et al. (2022), in their cross-sectional study including a sample of three hundred twenty (n=320) undergraduate students from a state university's Faculty of Health Sciences, Nursing Department found that 55.3% of students (177) possessed an unfavourable attitude towards online education. Students between the age group of 25 and 29 had significantly greater attitude scores than those between the age groups of 17 and 20 and 21 and 24 ($p = 0.002$). Students who used computers had considerably higher attitude scores than those without computers ($p = 0.001$).

Yadav & Albatti (2025), in their mixed-methods study with a sample of seventy-five (n= 75) students from a range of academic fields found that students frequently utilized EdTech tools. 96.1% of students stated that they used digital resources to enhance their speaking, listening, writing, and reading language.

Kaur (2024), conducted a correlational study among two hundred ninety-two (n=292) college students from 11 Punjabi colleges, the findings revealed that attitudes with regard to e-learning differed significantly depending on whether one had better, good, or worse study habits. Also, it was found that college students who have better study habits have a higher attitude toward e-learning.

Kumari (2022), in her experimental study conducted among eight hundred (n=800) Patna district students found that although the study habits of adolescents appeared to be appropriate, the impact of e-learning on them was found to be significantly high.

Ilo et al. (2018), in their descriptive study conducted among twenty-five percent (25%) of the total population with a sample of three hundred (n=300) students of SS1 and SS2 250 each found a strong positive correlation between students' better study habits and their utilization of ICT. Fifty-two (31.9%) of the respondents used ICT to compare notes from lectures, while 156 (32.7%) use it to read various materials online. Others use it for chat, email, and various other tasks.

Ward et al. (2025), in their mixed-methods study conducted on seventy-one (n=71) university students from various demographics found that 83% of students who used AI tools in their study routines improved their academic performance. 35% showed a modest improvement and 48% reported a significant improvement. Only seventeen percent of respondents said their academic performance was unchanged.

Kursoro (2019), in a correlational study conducted among three hundred seventy-five (n=375) students in Bukwo District, Uganda, demonstrated that social media was frequently used for a variety of purposes. Students have good study habits (mean of 3.18). $R = 0.985$ and the R^2 value of 0.985 at the significance level of 0.000 supported the correlation results, which reveals a substantial association between social media and students' study habits.

Mbah (2010), in survey study performed on hundred (n=100) CST/Biology department students revealed that students generally had a positive outlook towards ICT and used them to improve their learning. As a result, based on the kind of ICT they used to aid their studies, students frequently changed their study habits.

Hero et al. (2021), in their descriptive correlational study conducted on one hundred and twelve (n=112) junior high school students from a private school in the Obando, Bulacan, Philippines district found that students had good study habits and they frequently engaged in class debates. Furthermore, a high or significant correlation was found between students' study habits and the integration of the e-learning system.

Finally, Amyot et al. (2017), in their correlational study conducted among two hundred twelve (n=212) second year dental students (SP14, n=106) and (SP15, n=106) found that in comparison to 62% of the SP14 class, 72% of the SP15 class reported watching all or more than half of the scheduled lectures, with the majority watching multiple lectures every week. Students in SP14 and SP15 responded that they were unlikely to read the assigned readings prior to the class.

Summary of patterns

Collectively, the findings affirmed that students had a favourable attitude towards e-learning, which also helped them in developing better study habits. However, some studies found neutral or unfavourable attitude primarily because of factors like lack of resources, various levels of internet access, and technical issues.

CONCLUSION

This meta-analysis aimed to explore the attitude of students towards e-learning and its impact of their study habits by analysing findings from sixteen (n=16) empirical studies conducted across various educational levels, cultural backgrounds, and methodological frameworks.

Overall, the study revealed a significant and generally positive relationship between attitude and study habits of students. Research conducted by Kumar & Pandey (2024), Kar & Saha (2014), and Kaur (2024) demonstrated that students considered e-learning as effective and engaging, and helped them in improving their study habits and academic behavior. A few studies, on the other hand such as Gullu et al. (2022) and Eraslan & Topkaya (2017), found neutral or unfavourable attitudes, mainly because of institutional support issues and technology constraints.

On a practical level, the conclusions of this study offer important implications for educators, curriculum developers, and academic advisors. The body of research demonstrates that while e-learning has rapidly gained acceptance and proven beneficial in developing positive study habits, its potential is fully realized only when supported by sufficient technology, training, and institutional enthusiasm. Future efforts should focus on improving teacher preparedness, ensuring fair access to digital resources, embedding e-learning effectively within curricula, and continually assessing its pedagogical effectiveness across varied learning environments.

It should be acknowledged that the scope of this meta-analysis's generalizability may be limited because it was based on qualitative synthesis rather on quantitative effect size pooling. To further investigate the causal relationship, future research would benefit by employing statistical meta-analytic techniques, diving deeper into moderating variables, and including longitudinal data to better examine the link between e-learning and study habits.

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